

Objective and Subjective Factors Affecting the Development of Personal and Professional Training of Academic Lyceum Students

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Abstract:

In this article, the psychological foundations, psychological possibilities and qualities of the psychological phenomenon of the development of personal and professional training of academic lyceum students are applied.

Keywords: personal qualities, professional qualities, mental qualities, moral qualities, humanity, humanitarianism.

Today, researching the field of personality and being able to forecast the possibilities of its development is the result of many ills occurring in society, including indifference to the fate of others, failure to help others, negative experiences caused by the personal and professional training of students. secretly harming others, insisting on being only "myself" in any case, serves to optimize measures aimed at preventing internal destructive disorders in the individual. Accordingly, in this chapter, we will analyze the views that are the conceptual basis of our psychocorrection program, which provides an opportunity to correct the phenomenon of egoism in a person.

Child care. In this case, adults should create an opportunity for the child to act on his own for years, teach him to perform independent actions from the age of 2-3. As he grows up, he is involved in more complex tasks - cleaning the house, going to the store, helping with something, and of course the child is encouraged with praise. If less attention is given, children may develop selfishness as a defense reaction to insufficient attention.

Develop empathy. This is an important component that helps to get rid of egoism. Sometimes a person has to force himself to develop alternative behaviors. If a person always moves with his mind, he will never be able to move upward

Personal spirituality develops objectively under the influence of many factors and tools. Because of this, the concept of spirituality is characterized by multifacetedness. "Land, family, parents, children, relatives, neighbors, people, conscience, loyalty to our independent state, respect for people, trust, memory, freedom, this is the broad meaning of spirituality. . Only when a person feels that he is a part of the nation, thinks about it, and lives in harmony, does he feel spiritual.

In her later works, A.K. Markova defines professional training as "a mental state that allows for independent and responsible action, consists of the results of human labor, and determines the ability and competence of a person to perform certain labor tasks."

According to V. B. Gargai, "practice, when it is the object of a structured analysis, becomes a source of growth of the student's professional training: unreflective practice is useless and leads to professional stagnation of the student, not to development over time."

As part of the development of personal and professional training of academic lyceum students, the following can happen:

- 1) can reflect on the personal axiological system;
- 2) knows how to diagnose the system of the class's value orientation and develop the individual orientation of personal and professional qualities;
- 3) knows how to analyze the general cultural and professional organizers of the social environment;
- 4) knows how to conduct a moral and legal assessment of the events and effects of social reality.

The subjective system of values for the development of personal and professional training of academic lyceum students, the hierarchy of his professional motives, psychological views, emotions, a unique set of assumptions, personally significant approaches to solving pedagogical tasks, intentions and actions uniqueness, individual unrepeatable style of preferred psychological interaction, optimal methods of students' compatibility with each other - all this determines the process of development of personal-professional preparation of academic lyceum students.

In this way, it can be defined as a harmonious part of the development of personal and professional preparation of academic lyceum students.

The development of personal and professional preparation of academic lyceum students was considered together with synonymous concepts such as individualism, narcissism, egocentrism, individual uniqueness or motivational state.

Individualism - (French, individualism, Latin *individuum* - indivisible), is a type of worldview, the essence of which is to contrast the position of the individual with society. Individualism is manifested in moral behavior in real-life situations, in various concepts such as moral, philosophical, ideological, and political.

The concept of narcissism was introduced into the direction of psychoanalysis by Z. Freud, who claims that it shows the inner image of a person. Later, this term began to be used in different meanings. According to J. Zilburg, one of the manifestations of another stream of psychoanalysis is narcissism or grandiose mania and the desire to maintain one's ability to do many things. The concept of narcissism is used in the psychoanalytic literature to refer to four specific phenomena: as a criterion for different self-evaluations (for example, when a narcissist overestimates or underestimates in a state of self-doubt); in order to determine the libidinal stage of development; in describing a narcissist; showing sexual deviance;

For example, J. Godefroy accepted the study of egocentrism as a characteristic of subjective perception of a person, which serves to establish the connection between the child himself and external objects. According to J. Piaget, a representative of psychoanalysis, personal qualities are an age-related feature of intellectual development.

T.I. Pashukova studies personal training as a cognitive, moral and communicative feature. According to T. I. Pashukova, egocentrism is an emotional manifestation of a person's condition.

A.A. Chanishev sees students as a personal characteristic of personal-professional training and his moral motivation, while L.A. Bloom interprets personal-professional training as a philosophical doctrine as an integral part and principle of personal life.

In psychology, the development of personal and professional training of students is considered as an individual behavior that causes a type of negative behavior of socially destructive significance, and it occurs individually in a person.

Z. Freud, one of the representatives of psychoanalysis, who deeply analyzed the ideas of developing the personal and professional training of his students, interprets the personal and professional training of students in a broad sense and claims that this behavior is the individuality of each individual.

C. D. Broad distinguishes the desires of people related to things or people and calls them personal motivation-stimulators:

the first is property relations, in which a person creates positive characteristics that belong to him.

the second is kinship, and a person wants more welfare for his children than for other children.

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